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Health literacy paradox & institutional betrayal reveal patient-centered opportunities for epistemic equity

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This paper examines the discord between institutional rhetoric of inclusion, health literacy, and patient-centeredness in healthcare and the realities of being an informed patient with complex multimorbidity. 182 participants who live with hypermobile Ehlers-Danlos Syndrome reported their symptoms and comorbidities and completed a series of validated scales for biopsychosocial functioning including the Health Literacy Questionnaire and Institutional Betrayal Questionnaire - Healthcare. Health literacy clusters are defined by scores on nine subscales: three related to taking action and managing health; three related to health information; and three related to social or relational aspects of health literacy. Findings revealed a health literacy paradox: high capacity to appraise information and understand health information enough to know what to do was undermined if not paired with adequate interpersonal and health-related social support. Low health-related support was predicted by institutional betrayal ($OR=1.39$, $p=.003$), lack of interpersonal support ($OR=0.88$, $p=.001$), and high diagnostic delay ($OR=7.19$, $p<.001$). Those in the Low Support cluster were of average age and did not have more symptoms or comorbidities than those in the high and moderate groups; however they had the highest impact of symptoms and institutional betrayal, the longest diagnostic delay (average 15.1 years, $SD=12.1$), highest level of undiagnosed neuraxial symptoms (neurological, spinal, and orthostatic), and the lowest scores for each of six separate measures of support and all measures of physical health and self-efficacy. This is counter to other analyses of these data, which indicate if support is lacking in one area, compensatory support is accessed in another.

The greatest risk factor is the absence of protective factors. Informational literacy is less of a barrier for hypermobile patients, who are often highly informed and able to appraise complex health information. Barriers, rather, are attitudinal and cultural, reflected in narrow understandings of hypermobility and neurodiversity within healthcare institutions, limited ability to navigate these systems without support, and institutional practices that reinforce stigma, stereotypes, and dominant normative discourses that no longer reflect clinical reality (and maybe never did). Interpersonal, social, and navigational support serve as protective factors, mitigating other risk factors, particularly for non-binary and housebound or bedbound patients. Opportunities for epistemic justice are revealed by the identification of epistemic injustice. This study identifies unmet needs and clear opportunities for epistemic equity initiatives (especially for highly informed patients) that may serve as a turning point for institution-centered inclusion rhetoric to become patient-centered reality.

Introduction

In the landmark 2020 paper, *Implementing value-based health-care at scale*,¹ Koff and Lyons describe value-based care as improving four key areas: health outcomes; experiences of receiving care; experiences of providing care; and effectiveness and efficiency of care. Health literacy is presumed to be an unalloyed good and an enabler of improvement in all four of these domains. Yet, highly informed patients can find their knowledge has a paradoxical effect, becoming a barrier in clinical settings rather than improving care and health outcomes. Patients experiencing the uncertainty of diagnostic delay and complex multimorbidity may be inclined to research their own symptoms before or after consulting medical appointments, bringing research papers to clinical consultations in an attempt to participate in their own care and contribute to improving the four domains of value-based care, particularly the efficacy of future diagnostic investigations. However, even when providing sources from peer reviewed journals, or when the studious patient by night is also a physician or epidemiologist by day, knowledge provided from patients to providers is frequently perceived as a sign of health catastrophizing, with clinicians dismissing both the research provided and the patient who provided it.

Institutional rhetoric of inclusion is common across academic and healthcare institutions. Often aspirational in nature, such rhetoric highlights existing blind spots and opportunities to improve, rather than reflecting the daily reality of institutional culture and systems. Well-intentioned yet counterproductive approaches to inclusion abound, and small practical changes can transform aspiration into effective action in clinical settings.

Of 958 potential research questions identified in 2024 by hypermobile patients, researchers, and clinicians, ranked in the top 10 was the question: “*Why do health professionals demonstrate a strong aversion towards individuals with chronic pain and/or fatigue in conjunction with generalized joint hypermobility?*”² Traditional assumptions about patients who have been ‘problematized’ due to their background, symptoms, or circumstances reinforces deficit orientations, stereotypes, cultures of exclusion, and marginalizing practices,³ reinforcing stereotype threat, rather than using its presence as a cue to change course. Stereotype threat surfaces as quickly as a doctor can swap their scrubs for a hospital gown, and it can be addressed just as quickly.

Healthcare rhetoric about patient-centredness is often aspirational rather than based on patient reality, clinical relevance, or the impact of misrepresentation on patients or clinicians. Inclusion initiatives typically center the excluders, aiming to relocate the excluded into the dominant institutional culture, rather than interrogating how institutional practices perpetuate inequities and reinforce exclusion.³ They might pull the red velvet rope across for one person, but the structure and purpose of the rope and the systems that keep it in place go unquestioned. It is high time to call into question the misinformed and misunderstood versions of inclusion and patient-centeredness practiced in

healthcare and medical research.

Do informed patients pose a threat? Or are they an untapped resource? What’s really going on when higher health literacy does not translate into improving health outcomes? This is the real question. As a starting point, this study investigates health literacy, institutional betrayal and support in patients with hypermobile Ehlers-Danlos Syndrome and high rates of neuraxial multimorbidity and diagnostic delay.

Participants and Methods

This study was conducted as part of a research project about care and management priorities for hypermobile Ehlers-Danlos Syndrome (hEDS) and hypermobility-related multimorbidity. Responsible design (including lived expertise and representation of patients who have been traditionally excluded from research) was prioritized in study design, recruitment, in both the data and decision making. Patients and clinicians comprised the core research team, patient stakeholders contributed to design decisions and analytical interpretations, and publications were co-produced by patients and clinicians who live and work with hEDS.

In this international study, 182 participants with hEDS completed a series of online surveys, followed by an optional semi-structured interview. Support was offered for those who wanted to participate in other ways and the survey could be stopped and resumed in multiple sittings, to increase accessibility. Patients reported their symptoms, comorbidities, access, management, and healthcare experiences and completed a series of validated scales for biopsychosocial functioning including the Health Literacy Questionnaire (HLQ), Institutional Betrayal Questionnaire - Healthcare (IBQ-H). Completion rates varied across the surveys: 182 completed the HLQ, some were lost to follow up, 146 completed the full series of validated scales. (See Supplementary materials for a full list of validated survey instruments used in this study.)

Analysis was conducted using R version 4.4.1. Validated surveys were scored using the *psych* package. Kmeans cluster analyses were conducted with Ward’s-D method. Optimum clustering level was identified by Eigenvalues. Illustrative vignettes were constructed using the HLQ Ophelia Method⁴ and composite themes from open answer questions and interview responses.

Results

Low support-related health literacy was strongly predicted by low interpersonal support, experiences of institutional betrayal, and diagnostic delay of more than 14 years (Table 1). Patients with high diagnostic delay had 7.19 times higher odds of being members of the Low Support cluster. Health literacy scores for this cohort of hypermobile adults found several overall patterns, and patterns unique to each cluster. Overall, the highest score were for Subscales A9 Understand health information enough to know what to do; and I5 Appraisal of health information; followed by the

Variables	OR ¹²	95% CI ²	p-value
Gender			
Female / Male	1.61	0.12, 21.0	>0.999
Female / Non-binary	0.66	0.09, 4.56	>0.999
Male / Non-binary	0.41	0.02, 8.94	>0.999
Current Age (in years)	0.96	0.88, 1.03	0.305
Age at diagnosis (in years)	0.99	0.92, 1.08	0.732
High diagnostic delay	7.19***	2.34, 25.0	<0.001
Interpersonal support	0.88**	0.80, 0.95	0.001
Institutional betrayal	1.39**	1.13, 1.75	0.003
Impact of symptoms			
Physical functioning	1.02	0.95, 1.09	0.626
Impact of hypermobility	1.00	0.98, 1.03	0.757
Orthostatic intolerance	0.98	0.95, 1.04	0.795
Impact of fatigue	1.02	0.92, 1.04	0.532
Cognitive deficits	1.00	0.97, 1.08	0.436
Self-efficacy with symptoms	1.00	0.94, 1.05	0.865

¹ *p<0.05; **p<0.01; ***p<0.001

² OR = Odds Ratio, CI = Confidence Interval

Table 1 Factors predicting health literacy clusters

Membership of the Low Support health literacy cluster (Cluster 2, with the lowest scores on the Health Literacy Questionnaire support subscales) was strongly predicted by low interpersonal support and high diagnostic delay of more than 14 years. Patients with high diagnostic delay had 7.19 times higher odds of having low health-related social support.

remaining Action and Information Health Literacy Subscales: I8 Ability to find good health information; and A3 Actively managing health; Overall the lowest scores were for A7 Navigating the healthcare system; and S6 Actively engage with healthcare providers. Kmeans cluster analysis identified three clusters which we have named High Support, Mid Support, and Low Support, as variation between clusters was almost entirely delineated by variation in the Social Support Health Literacy Subscale.

Support-based health literacy clusters

Health literacy clusters are defined by scores on nine subscales: three related to taking action and actively managing health; three related to accessing, understanding, and appraising information; and three related to social or relational aspects of health literacy. The health literacy clusters were named High support, Mid support, and Low support because they were delineated primarily by the scores of the support subscales (Figure 4). Additional measures of support were also analyzed by cluster, as well as diagnostic delay impact of symptoms, self-efficacy with pain and with the top two most interfering symptoms, experiences of institutional betrayal trauma related to healthcare, neuraxial symptoms and overall multimorbidity (Table 2). The support and belonging scale was negatively correlated to the impact of hypermobility (Figure 3).

All measures of support, impact of symptoms, and self-efficacy were most impaired in the Low Support Cluster. This cluster had the longest average diagnostic delay (15.1 years), but they were of average age, and had an average number of comorbidities for all categories except undiagnosed neuraxial symptoms. This group also had the

Variables	Health Literacy Clusters		
	High Support (N=34)	Mid Support (N=88)	Low Support (N=60)
	Mean (SD)		N(%)
Age (in years)	33.4 (11.7)	38.6 (11.5)	34.1 (11.0)
Gender			
Female	30 (88.2%)	73 (83.0%)	50 (83.3%)
Male	1 (2.9%)	8 (9.1%)	2 (3.3%)
Non-binary	3 (8.8%)	7 (8.0%)	8 (13.3%)
Professionally active			
Working or Studying	29 (85.3%)	55 (62.5%)	37 (61.7%)
Unable to work	5 (14.7%)	22 (25.0%)	21 (35.0%)
Bedbound	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	5 (8.3%)
Housebound	2 (5.9%)	2 (2.3%)	3 (5.0%)
Mostly housebound	3 (8.8%)	15 (17.0%)	13 (21.7%)
Age at diagnosis (in years)	27.7 (11.5)	32.3 (11.6)	28.2 (10.5)
Years with symptoms	23.8 (14.7)	28.4 (13.9)	26.4 (13.7)
Delay in diagnosis (in years)	9.66 (10.2)	13.6 (12.8)	15.1 (12.0)
0-4 years			
	14 (41.2%)	23 (26.1%)	14 (23.3%)
15 years or longer			
	8 (23.5%)	29 (33.0%)	28 (46.7%)
Impact of symptoms			
Physical functioning (0-100)	28.7 (17.8)	23.3 (15.3)	16.8 (9.91)
Hypermobility (0-360)	232 (46.6)	242 (37.1)	261 (33.4)
Orthostatic intolerance (0-100)	60.1 (16.3)	64.6 (17.9)	71.3 (13.0)
Fatigue (0-100)	50.0 (19.8)	52.2 (15.3)	60.7 (12.8)
Cognitive deficits (0-100)	63.5 (18.1)	63.1 (13.6)	69.3 (11.4)
Self-efficacy			
...despite pain (0-60)	35.0 (13.1)	29.7 (12.8)	25.8 (13.4)
...despite worst symptom (0-60)	29.3 (13.7)	23.1 (13.5)	18.6 (12.5)
...second worst symptom (0-60)	32.2 (14.7)	29.3 (15.5)	20.6 (13.7)
Healthcare experiences			
Institutional betrayal (0-12)	4.64 (2.89)	5.18 (2.79)	7.77 (2.56)
Trusted institution before event	15 (72.7%)	57 (74.0%)	25 (53.2%)
Never returned after event	12 (54.5%)	31 (40.3%)	25 (53.2%)
Perceived support			
Interpersonal support (0-36)	30.5 (5.60)	25.3 (7.40)	19.4 (7.65)
Health social support (0-14)	10.7 (0.7)	8.6 (1.0)	6.3 (1.3)
....from family (0-100)	84.6 (20.9)	66.6 (29.1)	51.3 (31.0)
....from community (0-100)	51.1 (28.8)	34.1 (26.8)	30.0 (27.9)
....from workplace (0-100)	48.3 (32.9)	30.8 (29.5)	25.2 (28.4)
....from clinicians (0-100)	79.5 (15.2)	53.6 (23.7)	31.5 (23.2)
Multimorbidity			
Body areas affected (0-12)	9.5 (1.8)	9.6 (1.9)	9.9 (2.0)
All symptoms+diagnoses	21.0 (7.1)	19.8 (6.3)	22.4 (6.7)
Laxity symptoms (0-7)	5.4 (1.5)	4.7 (1.5)	5.2 (1.5)
ProLapse symptoms (0-8)	2.1 (1.4)	1.7 (1.4)	2.1 (1.3)
Neuraxial diagnoses (0-17)	4.4 (2.7)	3.6 (2.0)	4.2 (2.2)
Neuraxial symptoms (0-13)	6.3 (3.2)	6.5 (3.2)	7.7 (3.0)

Table 2 Participant demographics stratified by health literacy
Pain measures were also recorded, but have been omitted due to lack of variance and lack of correlation with other measures.

Figure 3 Support and belonging and impact of hypermobility
Interpersonal support and belonging subscale (ISEL) decreases as Bristol impact of hypermobility (BloH) increases

Figure 4 Health literacy clusters

Health literacy clusters showed the greatest variation based on the HLQ Support subscales (S1, S4, S6), and information and action subscales that are strongly related to support (I2, A7), and were associated with measures of fatigue (FSS, MFIS), cognitive deficits (PDQ), physical functioning (SF36 PCS), interpersonal support (ISEL I2), and institutional betrayal in healthcare (IBQ-H).

HLQ Support/Relational subscales (1, 4, 6):

- S1 Understood and supported by healthcare providers;
- S4 Social support for health;
- S6 Actively engage with healthcare providers.

HLQ Action subscales (3, 7, 9):

- A3 Actively managing health;
- A7 Navigating the healthcare system;
- A9 Understand health information enough to know what to do.

HLQ Information subscales (2, 5, 8):

- I2 Having sufficient information to manage my health;
- I5 Appraisal of health information;
- I8 Able to find good health information

Abbreviations: FSS, Fatigue Severity Scale, MFIS, Modified Fatigue Impact Scale; HLQ, Health Literacy Questionnaire; IBQ-H institutional Betrayal Questionnaire-Healthcare; ISE, Interpersonal Support Evaluation List; PDQ, Perceived Deficit Questionnaire; SF36 PCS, Short Form 36 Physical Components Score.

Figure 5 Institutional betrayal in healthcare clusters

Institutional betrayal cluster 2 and cluster 5 had the most negative experiences, and most members from Health Literacy cluster 2. When interacting with healthcare institutions, 84.8% of patients report having their experience denied, dismissed, negated, invalidated in some way or being labeled a 'problem patient'. The majority report healthcare institutions creating environments that normalize negative experiences (74.0%), make negative experiences more likely (66.4%), make it difficult to report concerns (58.9%), or respond inadequately to concerns or reports of negative experiences (58.9%).

Interpersonal support is a key protective factor.

It can boost self-efficacy and mitigates the trauma of Institutional Betrayal (doesn't stop it from happening, but effectively mitigates the harm)

It can increase ability to navigate health systems, find good health information, and translate good information into good healthcare experiences

IBQ-H Action/Inaction subscales (1, 5, 6):

- 1A Not taking proactive steps to prevent negative experiences;
- 5A Responding inadequately to reports or concerns;
- 6A Mishandling protected personal information.

IBQ-H Deny/Dismiss subscales (8, 11):

- 8D Deny, dismiss, or invalidate you experience in some way;
- 11D Discriminate, stereotype, no treated like a valued member;

IBQ-H Environment subscales (2, 3, 12):

- 2E Creating an environment where negative experiences seem common;
- 3E Creating an environment where negative experiences seem likely;
- 12E Creating an environment that made it difficult to seek care.

IBQ-H Reporting subscales (4, 9):

- 4R Made it difficult to report or share concerns;
- 9R Punishing you for reporting concerns or negative experiences.

IBQ-H Institutional Reputations subscales (7, 10):

- 7I Covering up adverse medical events;
- 10I Suggesting your experience might affect the institution's reputation.

highest institutional betrayal score, and were least likely to trust healthcare institutions before and after experiencing negative events there. The High Support and Mid Support Clusters had higher levels of trust in institutions (72.7% to 74.0%) before experiencing negative events, and that trust was shaken so that 40.3 to 54.5% never returned to those institutions after the negative experience.

Hannah is a representative member of the High support health literacy group. Hannah is 33 years old, studying part-time and does a little freelance graphic design from home because commuting has never worked for her body. She leans on her family, and they are always there for her whenever something glitches or flares up or she needs help getting a stray rib or cuboid back in place. Hannah received diagnoses for hEDS, MCAS, POTS and PCOS about five or six years ago and has an amazing health team now. After a whole lotta years and countless doctors and ‘normal’ test results, she finally found a doc that connected the dots in a way that finally made sense. Such a relief! It’s taken a while to put the team together, but it’s finally in the sweet spot. They don’t talk directly to each other (yet), but they all *get it* and she doesn’t get mixed messages or crossed wires anymore where one doctor contradicts the other and she’s stuck in the middle. Ugh. Hannah can bring interesting research to her doctors, and they add it to their notes and consider the implications of new research findings for her care. Hannah’s physiotherapist is also hypermobile which has made all the difference; she’s been able to get treatments and exercises that don’t cause flares or injuries for the first time in her life. Most of Hannah’s symptoms don’t even bother her most days, so much so that she can forget how delicate the balance is! If she overdoes it, or misses her meds or Tuesday Feldenkrais sessions, the crash is pretty bad (nowhere near as bad as the falling-off-a-cliff crashes used to be before she knew about POTS or hEDS, but still pretty gnarly), with three or four days recovery time (better than months. She can still have a life and plan around a few glitchy days.) If things get tough, or if the brain is particularly foggy, Hannah knows who to call and is surrounded by amazing people she can turn to and count on.

Institutional betrayal, someone to turn to

Institutional betrayal was ubiquitous, with 84.8% of participants reporting having their experiences denied, invalidated, disbelieved or dismissed during healthcare encounters. Institutional betrayal was also correlated with low support, and 77% of the participants in the Low support health literacy cluster were also in the highest institutional betrayal clusters (Figure 5).

As with health literacy, institutional betrayal was also correlated with all measures of support. In both cases, in the Low Support cluster, scores for interpersonal support, health-related support, institutional betrayal, physiological functioning, hypermobility, orthostatic intolerance, fatigue, and cognitive deficit all demonstrated not only the greatest negative impact compared to the other Health Literacy Clusters, but also greater negative impact than those patients with the longest diagnostic delay (see Chapter 4.1)

Alex is a representative member of the Low support

health literacy group. Alex just turned 34 last month and has been unable to work for about ten years. Most days Alex needs to lie down in the afternoon for a few hours, and it’s totally unsafe to drive at that time. Alex mentioned this ‘sundowning’ to the GP, but they just dismissed it and said “You’re too young to have dementia” without doing any tests or real checking or anything. Alex got diagnosed with hEDS six years ago after getting the run around and an eight month waiting list. The rheumy appointment finally came, and they scribbled hEDS and then nothing. No plan. Nada. Just ‘come back in five years or sooner if things get worse.’

Alex also has stage 3 lipedema, but can’t get any help for that either. All the clinics only take cancer patients. Even just getting a referral to a lymphatic massage therapist has been impossible. They all want 40 forms before even getting an appointment. It’s all too much, fully headed for a meltdown. Alex has done every online screening test for

Variables	Healthy Norms	Health Literacy Clusters	
		High Support (N=34)	Low Support (N=60)
	Median [IQR]	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)
Impact of symptoms			
Physical functioning (0-100)	62.8 (17.8)	28.7 (17.8)	16.8 (9.91)
Hypermobility (0-360)	81 [57.25]	232 (46.6)	261 (33.4)
Fatigue (0-100)	15.3 (12.0)	50.0 (19.8)	60.7 (12.8)
Self-efficacy			
...despite pain (0-60)	40.1 (11.0)	35.0 (13.1)	25.8 (13.4)
...despite worst symptom (0-60)		29.3 (13.7)	18.6 (12.5)
...second worst symptom (0-60)		32.2 (14.7)	20.6 (13.7)
Multimorbidity			
Body areas affected (0-12)	2	9.5 (1.8)	9.9 (2.0)
Other norms	JHS	MS	
Hypermobility (0-360)	231.5		
Body areas affected (0-10) [†]	9		
Pain self-efficacy (0-60)		30	

[†]excluding ribs and head

Table 6 Hypermobile patients compared to healthy norms and MS

Hypermobile patients showed significantly higher fatigue scores (50.0 - 60.7 compared to 15.3) and severely reduced physical functioning scores (16.8 - 28.7 compared to 62.8 out of 100) across all clusters compared to population normative data, with a four-fold difference in fatigue and physical functioning for the Low Support cluster. Impact of hypermobility scores were much higher than population norms, the Low Support cluster also scored 30 points higher than patients with JHS. Self-efficacy scores for pain and most interfering symptoms indicate greater impairment than both population norms and patients with Multiple Sclerosis.

autism and knows they should make it official, (but they hate everything about hospitals, the lights, the sounds, those horrible chairs, who ever thought a human body could withstand that?) but after the last diagnostic odyssey they’re not ready to start another quest like that. Besides, with great diagnosis comes great... well, no, no responsibility. No plan either. No management. Nobody gets it. Nobody helps. The endless explaining and advocacy is exhausting, it’s all so unfair, entirely unjust, and advocacy and explanations don’t seem to make any difference, because nobody helps anyway. It shouldn’t be this way. Alex has no idea who to call if

something goes wrong. And no way of knowing how close to the edge things are getting or any way to prevent or reduce symptom flares. Alex always has to pace themselves, and knows they can't borrow spoons from tomorrow (see Spoon Theory⁵), so they are constantly calculating the trade-off between doing one thing today and the inevitable recovery tax tomorrow. If they don't manage their spoons, the consequences are disastrous; last time it took four months before they could tolerate the supermarket again.

Discussion

Health literacy clusters revealed a paradox: high capacity to appraise information and understand health information enough to know what to do -- usually associated with high health literacy -- are undermined if not paired with adequate interpersonal support in life and health-related social support. Support also buffered the impact of institutional betrayal and boosted the ability to navigate the health system. All measures of physical health and self-efficacy were also found to be undermined by a lack of interpersonal and social support. Those in the low social health literacy group were of average age and did not have more symptoms or comorbidities than those in the high and moderate groups; however they had the highest impact of symptoms and institutional betrayal, the longest diagnostic delay, and the lowest scores for each of six separate measures of support. Like the overall SF36 measure provided less fidelity than the physical components score, measures of decontextualized support also lost fidelity in the averaging. By reporting support from family, community, workplace, and clinicians separately, we observed that some groups had zero in one category or another, but compensated for that with a high rating in another category. Community support was particularly protective for nonbinary participants, and those with the highest diagnostic delay or low support from family or clinicians. Everyone doesn't feel supported everywhere, but they find compensatory support somewhere. But these same data defy that compensatory trend when it comes to social health literacy or health-related social support.

Lack of interpersonal support and health-related social support are correlated with most biopsychosocial measures and experiences of institutional betrayal, suggesting that lack of support may amplify harmful effects of negative events and institutional betrayal in healthcare and also amplify the impact of symptoms. Contrary to clustering via management effectiveness of diagnostic delay, health literacy clusters reveal loss of compensatory support as a protective mechanism.

Navigating the health system, having sufficient information

Two health literacy subscales most closely associated with the support subscales (Figure 4) were A7 Navigate the health system, and I8 Able to find good health information. More than most any other scales, these two subscales are about action and information, both in ways that are heavily dependent on support from others. During interviews, most patients incidentally revealed that they, or someone in

their family or household, worked in or near the health system -- 'My mum's a doctor', 'my sister is a nurse', 'I work for the Ambulance service' -- suggesting that accessing a hEDS diagnosis at all requires insider information and access to a hidden network of support to effectively navigate the health system. Insider status and clinician capacity to navigate the health system was also conveyed in clinician surveys (as part of the wider study). Clinicians were not asked about their own diagnoses, symptoms, or experience as a patient, yet many disclosed their personal diagnosis and diagnoses of their family members in the open text questions, often as their first source of education about hypermobility, pain, and common comorbidities. These patient and clinician reports indicate the presence of an active yet hidden workforce of highly informed "patient navigators" providing "navigation support" for their families, personal networks, and communities of practice. Carers -- previously invisibilized, overworked, and unsupported workhorses of the health system -- are now acknowledged, supported and included by state health systems as crucial community-embedded members of the health workforce. Similarly, this study has identified a hidden workforce of highly informed community-embedded patient navigators supporting communities of patients and clinicians to connect with appropriate resources and supports for specific steps and stages of the patient journey, and to efficiently navigate clinically-relevant aspects of the health system. Like the hidden workforce of carers fill important unmet needs for individual patients that the health system does not or cannot provide, the hidden workforce of patient navigators fill important unmet needs for patient communities. Unlike carers, patient navigators are still invisible, overburdened, unacknowledged, and rarely supported by the health system they prop up. Patient and community navigators connect entire communities of patients to the radically protective benefits of interpersonal and health-related social support -- filling the unmet need for support and navigation that wasn't available to them as a patient -- often unsupported and leading to their own isolation and burnout. Patient partnership programs to reduce diagnostic uncertainty,^{6,7} and programs that acknowledge, support, and employ patient navigators in cancer communities and community navigators in Indigenous and childhood public health programs,⁸ have proven to be transformational collaborations, mutually enriching and generative for the navigators, the health system, and the communities involved. Initiatives that identify, connect and support this hidden workforce are a natural next step for hypermobile and neurodivergent communities, particularly those with less access to support networks or neuraxial multimorbidity.

Fatigue, orthostatic & cognitive impact on social support

Overall scores for physiological measures found profound impairment compared to population normative data, or even compared to patients with Multiple Sclerosis (Table 6), even in Cluster 1 where patients had the highest scores for health literacy, support, and physiological functioning. Curiously, symptoms most related to support

are the symptoms most impaired -- fatigue, cognitive, overall physical functioning, and self efficacy. Across all clusters, self-efficacy related to pain was far higher than the self-efficacy related to either of the top two most interfering symptoms. Pain is also less of an interference with social support, unlike fatigue or cognitive deficits that interfere with being upright or speech or memory, all of which are needed to maintain social connections and interpersonal support networks.

Patients in Cluster 2 had the lowest score in every health literacy subscale, which is atypical for the HLQ instrument, and for all prior subgroup analyses of these data. Compared to the other health literacy cluster, patients in Cluster 2 also had the lowest support scores (ISEL, CIQ), lowest physical functioning (SF36 PCS), and highest fatigue (FSS, MFIS). Intolerance had not been screened for, treated, or ruled out. This cluster has more undiagnosed neuraxial symptoms including numb-tingling related to undiagnosed entrapment neuropathies or compression syndromes, and inability to tolerate bright lights, sounds, or being upright, suggesting lack of support may prevent access to diagnosis or contribute to diagnostic delay. Cluster 2 also had a higher proportion of housebound and mostly housebound patients, and 100% of those who identify as being bedbound. The support and belonging subscale of the ISEL shows a correlation with the Bristol Impact of Hypermobility score -- higher support and belonging goes with lower impact of symptoms; lower support goes with higher impact of symptoms. Orthostatic intolerance (and associated dysautonomia) was strongly correlated with impact of hypermobility, self-efficacy, support, and institutional betrayal. Treating and managing orthostatic intolerance as a higher priority symptom may enable patients to tolerate being upright thus enabling access to the many protective benefits of interpersonal support. This finding also calls into question diagnoses of anxiety that may be premature without first ruling out, treating, or screening for orthostatic intolerance via physiological assessment and treatment responsiveness.

In addition to the standard Pain Self-Efficacy Score (PSEQ), a modified PSEQ was completed with identical questions but focusing on each of the top two most interfering symptoms. Self-efficacy for the worst symptom that interferes daily is an issue for all groups, with none coming close to the healthy norm of 40 (scale 0-60, higher is more self-efficacy). Only self-efficacy scores from the High Support Cluster were higher than the norm for patients with MS, but only for pain and their second worst symptom, not their worst. For the low group, both their first and second most interfering symptoms had a self-efficacy score that was half of the score from healthy controls, and two-thirds the score of patients with MS. Self-efficacy is also correlated to support, in the measures and in life. Feeling little to no control of the symptoms that interfere with support (like fatigue, dysautonomia, and cognitive symptoms) starts a mutual hampering loop, with lack of self-efficacy hampering support, and lack of support hampering self-efficacy. The presence of protective support

structures could derail and redirect that loop.

Patient-centered epistemic opportunities

Epistemic equity and epistemic justice are about how we generate, use, and share knowledge, and who we respect as knowers and generators of knowledge. Patients who need support feel least safe to reach out for it, or accept support when it is offered. Institutional betrayal is a form of betrayal trauma, and restoring capacity for safety -- to feel safe in your own skin, in your own home, as a member of the institutions you depend on -- is the first step of trauma-informed practice. Freyd and colleagues outline eleven steps of institutionalizing courage, as the natural next step when trust has been broken or, like the findings of this study, signs of institutional betrayal or lack of support have been identified.^{9,10} Of those eleven, patient-scientist initiatives and patient and community navigator programs operationalize inclusion rhetoric by putting the following steps into practice:

3. Add checks and balances to power structure and diffuse highly dependent relationships;
4. Respond well to victim disclosures (and create a trauma-informed reporting policy);
5. Bear witness, be accountable, apologize;
6. Cherish the whistle-blowers; cherish the truth-tellers;
10. Use the organization to address the societal problem.

Future studies could be improved by investigating both sides of institutional betrayal and institutional courage in response to negative experience in healthcare, examining where healthcare institutions responded appropriately to whistle-blowers and rewarded (as well as punished) those reporting negative experiences. Practical research is also needed to enable knowledge diversity and patient partnership at scale. While patient partnerships exist -- from diagnostics and patient-scientists to patient and community navigator programs -- they will continue to exist in the fringes unless and until they are represented in the research literature to justify policy change to identify best practice and make it common practice. Institutional courage is required to identify and support the community-embedded hidden workforce of patient navigators and create systems and processes that honor and value lived expertise in research, policy, practice, and clinical education. With potential to transform institutional rhetoric to truly patient-centered reality.

Widening inclusion (rather than just increasing) means focus on groups traditionally excluded or underrepresented or misrepresented in the sector. In the technology sector, 'previously excluded users' can provide insights that survivorship bias blinds others to. 'Previously excluded patients', like secret shoppers or white-hat hackers, are already stress testing the boundaries of the health system. Patient-scientists are generating breakthroughs from the first prevalence study,¹¹ to fibroblast cell adhesion studies, and discovering the first hEDS gene.¹² Visibility and support of the hidden patient navigation workforce and other patient-partnerships may be the key to harnessing knowledge diversity and enabling patient-centered policy, data, and care.

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